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Emotional Intelligence In Curriculum Development For Teacher Education

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated emotional intelligence in curriculum development for teacher education. Two research questions were answered and one hypothesis tested. The study adopted descriptive survey design with a population of 120 lecturers in the Faculty of Education, Rivers State University, Nkpolu-Port Harcourt. A sample size of 80 lecturers was drawn using the disproportionate stratified random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a 17- item questionnaire validated by three experts and it gave a reliability coefficient of 0.76 obtained using Cronbach Alpha method. The data collected were analyzed with mean and standard deviation, and z-test for the hypothesis. The findings showed that teacher educators exhibited knowledge and it's use in some of the areas of emotional intelligence for curriculum development for teacher education and that gender had effect on emotional intelligence in curriculum development for teacher education. It was then recommended that teacher educators should learn to improve on their organizational skills to avoid haphazard teaching and learning process, teacher educators should be open for trainings to enhance their conflict management skills, male teacher educators should learn to shelve their ego to encourage for mutual respect during curriculum development for teacher education etc.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, curriculum development, teacher education

INTRODUCTION

Emotional intelligence is a psychological construct that requires one to have awareness of self and others around. It is the ability of a person to perceive himself and manage same as well as to understand and empathize with others around the environment. It is presented here as a situation that warrants regulation for oneself and others too. Hagan and Hberle (2023) see emotional intelligence as ones capacity to recognize, control and communicate emotions and empathize as well as understand the feelings of other people. Emotions are the concerns when it comes to emotional intelligence; determinants of mood, circumstances or interactions with others around. In this light then emotional intelligence could be viewed

as the competence possessed by an individual either inherited or learned to manage characteristics of emotions both for oneself and for other people. This is what may have led to Duggal (2024) to conceive emotional intelligence as the ability to determine emotions in oneself and others, telling the effects and the application of knowledge to guide the thoughts and actions put forward. So, Keiling (2024) says that emotional intelligence helps a person to identify and understand the emotions other human beings put up. Thus, beyond a person's behavior and its impact, it also provides knowledge on how to deal with every emotional drive any other person may display. But much more evident from the foregoing definitions is that those who are not genetically gifted with certain characteristics of emotional intelligence can learn it. This also means that emotional intelligence can be taught using well designed curriculum for the purpose. This assertion above could easily be agreed upon considering that emotional intelligence is said to be composed of the following: self awareness, self regulation, motivation, empathy and social skills (Williams, 2022). This is supported by the study carried out by (Cherry, 2024) which confirms that emotional intelligence cannot only be developed or learnt but that it could be improved upon when a person is given to training in a given area of interest. Some of the steps identified that facilitate the development of emotional intelligence include: to listen actively, empathize, reflect among others. Also, Murtoff (2024) identified four very important skills that enhance emotional intelligence in people as self-management, self awareness, social awareness and relationship management.

- a. Self Management: When a person can control adequately without losing control of impulsive feelings and emotions, initiate and follow commitments by adapting to change in circumstances, then, such could be viewed as a self manager.
- b. Self Awareness: When an individual recognizes his own emotions and how they affect his thoughts and actions, yet, possessing enough confidence to deal with the said emotions even in the face of the available strength and weaknesses that is evident, then, the individual is said to possess self awareness.
- c. Social Awareness: A person who could understand others by putting himself in their situation when it comes to emotions, needs and concerns for others, and identifies with power dynamics in a group is socially aware.
- d. Relationship Management: People who are good at developing and maintaining good relationships, communicates unequivocally, inspire and influence others, work well in a team and could manage conflict effectively can be regarded as relationship managers.

Other skills that results from possessing emotional intelligence may include: emotional self control, adaptability, achievement orientation, positive outlook, influence coaching and mentorship, empathy, conflict management, team work, organizational awareness, inspirational leadership, self regard, self actualization, independence, social responsibility, problem solving, reality testing, flexibility, stress tolerance, optimism, decision making act (Craig, 2019). Most of the features identified are knowledge, skills and attitudes required for curriculum development to be effective, therefore, a curriculum developer is expected to combine these soft skills and pedagogical skills as well as professional skills to produce results or achieve desired outcomes in any classroom situation.

Curriculum development could be conceived as the thought out and intentional path created to bring about the desired quality of learning in a lesson delivery process. Nathani (2022) says that curriculum development is a process by which a teacher prepares a course for a program. This presents curriculum as the method adopted in teaching process to achieve desired objectives. Obiefuna (2009) had said curriculum development is the act of identifying, selecting and arranging what is meant to be taught to the learner and the creation of materials that would facilitate it. Perhaps this is the reason that made Nathani (2022) to further add that it is the procedural approach at organizing and improving the practice of the teacher in a classroom situation. For Akor, Ugboja and Okonny (2023) they observed that curriculum development is what gives rise to curriculum reviews, revision and reform of curriculum contents for it to be aligned with societal aspiration at a given time. Thus, Akor et al (2024) viewed curriculum

development as a process and practice of planning and delivering contents to the learners with the help of designed or created resources to enable learners be able to solve their problems and that of the society.

Therefore, curriculum development could be imagined as an act towards mixing ideas using the most apt method, technique, approach or strategy that would drive the point home very well to make experiences shared by the teacher to match with that which the learner has and can develop, enhance learning to become meaningful, experiential and objective. This process necessitates interaction between the teacher, the learner and the learning environment. So it could be viewed as a process tilted towards making sure that the teacher is able to share learning experiences that are relevant with the previous knowledge of the learner, thereby, removing hazy and hanging ideas possessed earlier by the learner and leading to the development of novel learning which agrees with the stated objectives for the lesson delivered.

So, curriculum development in this case is presented as the ability of the teacher to exercise some characteristics of emotional intelligence in content delivery such that the learner leaves the classroom satisfied with the teaching made available and the learning obtained. But the imbibing of a greater percentage of what is taught if not all of the characteristics of emotional intelligence is possible in an educational process through teacher education; a ground where individual teacher educators with varied characteristics come to meet with the learners and share the features they possess with them for their learning. Therefore, teacher education presents itself as a fertile ground to determining and nurturing emotional intelligence for the future.

Teacher education can be any arranged programme meant for preparing teachers at all levels. Akor, Okonny and Pepple (2023) regarded teacher education as an act meant for preparing and developing teachers for professional service delivery. Akor and Offor (2024) say teacher education is an embodiment of preparation of teachers in pedagogical skills, understanding of learners and the development of practical skills in the learner that is needed for teaching. In addition, (Akor & Okonny, 2024) presents that teacher education is the practice of training teachers to take up professional practice of teaching in the future. Hence, the process of teacher education is an equipping process of teachers in training to be able to meet the demands of the teaching professional for the now and the future. The intent of teacher education is to equip people with the passion, drive and grit to drawing out potentials that the learners possess in order to make them useful members of the society in the future. This act is in line with the goals of teachers education as stated below (FRN, 2016):

1. Produce highly motivated, conscientious and efficient classroom teachers for all levels of our educational system
2. Encourage further the spirit of enquiry and creativity in teachers
3. Help teachers fit into social life of the community and the society at large and enhance their commitment to national goals
4. Provide teachers with the intellectual and professional background adequate for their assignment and make them adaptable to changing situations.

These and many more are the goals of teachers and this is what curriculum development process in teacher education seeks to achieve by exposing them to the right characteristics among which are those of emotional intelligence needed in order to make the teacher a useful member of the society. In line with this, Kaplan (2019) had declared that emotional intelligence helps in closing the gap in education, particularly, in teacher education in the areas of teaching, training and learning, and how it has reformed education in widths and bounds. Also, Chen and Guo (2020) describe how emotional intelligence brings improvement to teaching in the dimensions of empathy, self awareness and self management while (Gomez et al, 2022; Toledo, 2023) affirmed how because of the complexities associated with emotional intelligence more studies was required but Sitti and Desiana (2023) believe there is need for curriculum management in the classroom when it comes to emotional intelligence. To buttress that point further Wood (2021) outlined some benefits of emotional intelligence in curriculum development to include teaching being healthier, responses to life challenges, feelings of confidence, resilience, better decision making, assertiveness and ability for cheerfulness among others. Beside these, it helps educators to be

passionate about what they do, building social skills, development of instructional techniques, developing novel adaptation skills, ensuring effectiveness towards meeting learner needs etc. These advantages presents the idea of emotional intelligence in curriculum development as a firm fulcrum to stand but does not seem to be known to all teacher educators.

Recently, in a chat with one teacher in training, it was discovered that some teacher educators do not have a strong grip on curriculum development process as it ought to. It was presented by the student that most times attending classes for lecture do not feel good except for the fact to they go there and write name as one of the persons present in the class. Further probe made it clear to the researchers that the teacher educators in question lacked some of the true personality of a teacher among which should be pedagogical skills, professional skills and so on. Upon trying to get more details on this, it was found that one of the major skills the said teacher educators lacked was emotional intelligence because these educators do not care about lateness to lecture, indiscipline in lecture hall, lack of attention to what is being taught and even lack of passion for the lecture process. So, even the students could tell this from observation that their educator lacked certain characteristics required which undermines such classes. Hence, the study to investigate emotional intelligence in curriculum development for teacher education. Specifically, the study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. Determine the extent of emotional intelligence exhibited in curriculum development for teacher education
2. Determine the extent of emotional intelligence possessed by male and female teacher educators in curriculum development for teacher education.

The following are the research questions that guided the study:

1. What is the extent of emotional intelligence exhibited in curriculum development for teacher education?
2. What is the extent of emotional intelligence possessed by male and female teacher educators in curriculum development for teacher education?

The study was guided by this hypothesis (P=0.05)

1. There is no significant difference between the extent of emotional intelligence possessed by male and female teacher educators in curriculum development for teacher education.

RESEARCH METHOD

The study was carried out in Rivers State University, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population for the study was made up of 120 lecturers from the Faculty of Education, Rivers State University while the sample size for the study was made up of 80 lecturers who were drawn using the disproportionate stratified random sampling technique from different departments of the faculty of education in the institution. The instrument used by the researcher for data collection was a questionnaire titled: Questionnaire on Emotional Intelligence in Curriculum Development for Teacher Education (QEICDTE) which was constructed by the researchers. It consists of 17 items which were arranged in two sections A and B. Section A contains the biodata, while section B consists of two subgroups on extent of emotional intelligence exhibited for curriculum development and the extent of emotional intelligence possessed by male and female teacher educators. The questionnaire was built on a modified four-point Likert Scale, namely: Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) and the levels of responses are weighted as 4, 3, 2, 1 respectively.

The instrument was face validated by three experts, one from Educational Psychology Unit and two from Curriculum and Instruction unit in the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba. The suggestions given were used in producing the final copy of the instrument. Cronbach alpha was used in calculating the reliability to determine the internal consistency which gave an alpha value of 0.76 which was considered high after it was administered on ten lecturers in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. The instrument was administered and collected back by the researcher on the spot. The data obtained were analyzed using, mean and standard deviation for

answering the research questions. Hence, $4+3+2+1=10/4=2.5$. Therefore, items whose mean were less than 2.5 were seen as Disagree (A) responses while those whose mean were 2.5 and above were seen as Agree (A) responses. The decision rule on the null hypotheses was to reject the hypothesis with calculated Z-value greater than the critical Z-value but otherwise accept.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the extent of emotional intelligence exhibited in curriculum development for teacher education?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard deviation on Extent of Emotional Intelligence Exhibited in Curriculum Development for Teacher Education

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	N	Remark
1.	Organized in all activities	1.9	1.3	LE	80
2.	Model for others to follow	3.2	1.9	HE	80
3.	Goal oriented	2.1	0.95	LE	80
4.	Display discipline culture	3.0	1.41	HE	80
5.	Integrate compliment with criticism	3.4	1.44	HE	80
6.	Open to others' opinion	3.3	1.45	HE	80
7.	Assertive for transformation	3.5	1.58	HE	80
	Grand Mean and S D	2.91	1.43		

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The result on table 1 above indicated that teacher educators exhibited these characteristics to the extent the result is shown here. From the result on display, except in the area of organization when it comes to curriculum development with mean (1.9) and ability to be focused on achieving curriculum development goals in the classroom with mean (2.1), in all the other areas, the teacher educators affirmed that there is above average performance. The implication is that the teacher educators should take time out to develop themselves to achieve success in their organizational ability and being goal oriented when it comes to curriculum development.

Research Question 2: *What is the extent of emotional intelligence possessed by male and female teacher educators in curriculum development for teacher education?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on Extent of Emotional Intelligence Possessed by Male and Female Teacher Educators in Curriculum Development for Teacher Education

S/N	Items	Male Lecturers			Female Lecturers			N
		Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark	
1.	Face challenging activities with perseverance	3.3	0.17	HE	2.1	0.95	LE	80
2	Exercise mutual respect	2.2	0.45	LE	3.2	0.22	HE	80
3	An active listener	3.5	0.17	HE	3.4	0.17	HE	80
4	Always curious	3.8	0.14	HE	3.5	0.24	HE	80
5	Lead team mindfully	3.4	0.18	HE	3.4	0.17	HE	80
6	Resolve conflict easily	1.9	1.3	LE	3.5	0.24	HE	80
7	Give others chance to express self	3.5	0.24	HE	3.3	0.17	HE	80
Grand Mean and Standard Deviation		3.08	0.37		3.2	0.30		

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The result on table 2 above showed that the respondents affirmed the extent to which male and female teacher educators possessed emotional intelligence in curriculum development for teacher education. The grand mean and standard deviation for both male and female (3.08 and 0.37, and 3.2 and 0.30) indicated that the teacher educators possessed the required extent of emotional intelligence in curriculum development for teacher education. However, there are indications of low extent in the areas of mutual respect and ability to resolve conflict on the part of the male teacher educators with mean (2.2 and 1.9) while their female counterpart seemed weak in the area of perseverance when faced with challenges with mean (2.1). Hence, improvement is required in these areas where the weaknesses were identified for the desired goals to be attained.

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between the extent of emotional intelligence possessed by male and female teacher educators in curriculum development for teacher education.

Table 3: Z-test on the Extent of Emotional Intelligence Possessed by Male and Female Teacher Educators in Curriculum Development for Teacher Education

Group	Mean	SD	N	df	Z _{calculated}	Z _{critical}	Decision
Male	3.08	0.37	38	78	12	1.96	Rejected
Female	3.2	0.30	42				

Source: Field data, 2024.

The result of table 3 shows that Z-calculated of 12 is greater than the Z-critical 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance at 78 degree of freedom indicating that there is significant difference on the extent of emotional intelligence possessed by male and female teacher educators in curriculum development for teacher education. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The result on table 1 revealed the extent to which emotional intelligence is exhibited in curriculum development for teacher education. The results indicated that the individuals saddled with curriculum development have low extent of organization and have poor goal oriented approach in curriculum development. But the general overview of emotional intelligence showed that they exhibited above

average level of emotional intelligence competence in curriculum development for teacher education. This was confirmed by the study carried out by Musa (2024) who found that teacher educators do well with emotional intelligence when they are trained in that line. Also, Smith and Kamm (2024) found that when teachers have emotional intelligence, it leads to improved relationship, classroom achievement, inner transformation and enhanced self management. So, it is expected that teacher educators should get trained through conferences and workshops in emotional intelligence to be ready to pass it on to their students both now and in the future.

The next result on table 2 showed the extent male and female teacher educators possessed emotional intelligence in curriculum development for teacher education. Based on the results, it was clear that there are indications that the teacher educators possess high extent of emotional intelligence in all the other areas but low extent when it comes to mutual respect and competence in resolving conflict for the male teacher educators while the female teacher educators showed weakness in perseverance when faced with challenges. This is a confirmation of the study by (Edanur, 2010) who found that when teachers possess emotional intelligence through training to manage their emotions and those of others they perform effectively. However, (Kgosiemang & Khoza, 2022) had a contrary result when they found that it was observed that primary school teachers had low extent of emotional intelligence; an output that may not be far from what their own teachers while in training had and transferred to them. The hypothesis result obtained in this study is in disagreement with what Edanur (2010) found which showed no significance between male and female teacher educators unlike the present one that indicated significance for the extent of emotional intelligence that male and female teacher educators possessed in curriculum development for teacher education. The implication is that it necessary for teacher educators to develop themselves adequately with regards to emotional intelligence knowing that it would enhance their capacity in curriculum development process..

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it could be concluded that teacher educators need to increase their knowledge and its usage when it comes to emotional intelligence to boost educational outcome. Also, particular areas of weakness identified with gender should be worked on for adequate result in performance of the teacher educators in curriculum development for teacher education in the future.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are the recommendations supporting the study based on the findings:

1. Teacher educators should learn to improve on their organizational skills to avoid haphazard teaching and learning process
2. Teacher educators should be open for trainings to enhance their conflict management skills.
3. Male teacher educator should learn to shelve their ego to encourage for mutual respect during curriculum development for teacher education.
4. Institutions where teachers are being trained should do regular performance appraisal to determine areas where the teacher educators are weak and then organize conferences and workshop to boost their competence in such areas.
5. Education stakeholders at all levels should join hands to fund trainings that would bring teacher educators, teachers in service and pre-service teachers together to bridge gaps observed in the society especially in the area of emotional intelligence.

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